

A STUDY ON E-GOVERNANCE AND ADMINISTRATIVE EFFICIENCY

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the role of e-Governance in administrative efficiency. The main objective of this study is to analysis the present issues and practical challenges between e-Governance and administrative efficiency. This study is a qualitative research and data were collected mainly from secondary sources. It argues that e-governance promotes participatory, transparent, responsive and inclusive democracy to enhance administrative efficiency. The accessibility of basic social services through the provision of information communication technology enhances effective communication between the government and the governed, while it creates open plain ground for the citizens to receive feedbacks from the appropriate government channel. The challenges arise from lack of trust, resistance to change, digital divide, cost, privacy and security. But, the challenges can be changed by enchanting necessary actions like awareness program and proper training, strengthening mobile government, ensuring website information in major languages, policy makers to ensure user friendly and congenial policy implementation, strengthening stakeholders and citizen feedback. The results suggest that e-Governance can be a very effective tool in improve administrative efficiency.

Keywords: E-Governance, Digital India, Policies, Indian Economy

INTRODUCTION

Governments throughout the world are in quest of finding ways to deliver public services more efficiently and effectively. E-governance is seen as a tool to improve productivity and efficiency in internal administration and to increase responsiveness to the public. E-governance can be understood as an extension of reforms to improve public sector efficiency. The initiatives of government agencies and departments to use ICT tools and applications, Internet and mobile devices to support good governance, strengthen existing relationships and build new partnerships within civil society, are known as e-governance initiatives. As with e-commerce, e-governance represents the introduction of a great wave of technological innovation as well as government reinvention. It represents a tremendous impetus to move forward in the 21st century with higher quality, cost effective government services and a better relationship between citizens and government (Fang, 2002). Many government agencies in developed countries have taken progressive steps toward the web and ICT use, adding coherence to all local activities on the Internet, widening local access and skills, opening up interactive services for local debates, and increasing the participation of citizens on promotion and management of the territory (Graham and Aurigi, 1997).

Application of e-governance has been a potent instrument in disseminating information, consultation, and enhancing citizen's participation, sending feedback to the citizens, monitoring and evaluating government projects and making government accountable and transparent in its total political engagements. E-governance has become a necessary political mechanism in evaluating government performance in many developed nations of the world, including United Kingdom, U.S.A, Netherland, Germany etc; it enhances citizen's ability to have access to the basic programmes of government while it brings about openness in performing public functions. The scope of e-governance revolves around e-

registration, e-participation, etaxation, e-mobilization, e-education, e-service delivery, e-feedback, e-policing, e-planning, edebate and analyses of public financial statements. It also creates awareness for the general local populace in relation to activities such as immunization, vaccination, civic education, time for collection of waste, identification of community development association in every neighborhood and making suggestions for the betterment of government programmes.

Despite the immense popularity and potency of electronic government, it remains uncharted in many countries regarding proper implementation. However, technology possesses the prospect of improvement in the way government works, and makes better interactions with their citizens. According to Siar (2005) the application of information and communication technology for improving governance by enhancing government's role in service delivery, public administration, and promotion of participatory democracy has been gaining momentum in many parts of the world. Maswood (2009) opines that E- governance may be understood as the performance of governance through the electronic medium in order to facilitate an efficient, speedy and transparent process of disseminating information to the public, and other agencies, and for performing government administration activities. It is the use of modern Information and Communication Technologies, such as Internet, Local Area Networks, and Mobiles etc, by Governments to improve effectiveness, efficiency and service delivery to promote easy access to the Government services to the public. E-Governance is a network of organizations to include government, nonprofit, and private-sector entities; in e-governance there are no distinct boundaries.

DEFINITION OF THE E-GOVERNANCE

The U.S. e-government Act, 2002 delineates e-government as “The use by the Government of web-based Internet applications and other information technologies, combined with processes that implement these technologies, to enhance the access to and delivery of Government information and services to the public, other agencies, and other Government entities or bring about improvements in Government operations that may include effectiveness, efficiency, service quality, or transformation;”. Whereas the European Union defines it as “E-Government is the use of Information and Communication Technologies in public administrations combined with organisational change and new skills in order to improve public services and democratic processes”. In the current era e-government has transformed from being “just another office tool” to a powerful utility for innovation, change and a tool for rejuvenating public sector. It is pertinently mentioned that e-governance and e-government are being used as a synonym in Indian perspective. E-Governance can be defined as; use of ICT in government in ways that either alters governance structures or processes in ways that are not feasible without ICT and create new governance structures or processes that were heretofore not possible without ICT and reify heretofore theoretical ideas or issues in normative governance.

ROLE OF E-GOVERNANCE

Owing to e-governance there is improvement in the internal organizational processes of Government, increased openness in government's functioning and enhanced political credibility & accountability in governance. The acronym SMRAT can expand as follows;

- **Simple:** Simplification of rules regulations and processes of government through the use of ICTs and thereby providing for a user- friendly government.
- **Moral:** Connoting emergence of an entirely new system of ethical values in the political and administrative machinery. Technology intervention improve the efficiency of anticorruption agencies police, judiciary etc.

- **Accountable:** Facilitating design development and implementation of effective Management Information System and performance measurement mechanisms and thereby ensuring accountability of public service functionaries.
- **Responsive:** Streamlining the processes to speed up service delivery and make system more responsive.
- **Transparent:** Bringing information hitherto confined in the government documents to the public domain and making processes and functions transparent, which in turn would bring equity and rule of law in responses of the administrative agencies.

Implications of E-Governance Projects on Indian Economy

AADHAAR: The most prominent of NeGP (National e-governance Plan) which was conceived by the planning commission of India whose aim is to provide a single unique identification to each resident of India. Aadhaar is one of the largest data base projects in the world with the budget of Rs.40 billion covers 1.26 billion population of India. Through this unique identification number residents can access up-to-date information about their entitlements, demand services and redress their grievances directly from their mobile phone, kiosks or other means.

PDS: (Public Distribution System): The core objective of this project is to enable the better services in the remote and rural areas of India with the use of ICT. Under the PDS which people below the poverty line will get food grains. The ministry of Food and Agriculture has now initiated computerization of the whole PDS network up to the Food Corporation of India (FCI). Technologies implemented like global positioning system for tracking movement of commodities, bar coded ration coupons, digitized ration card database and smart cards.

CARD: (digital registration of deeds) Project in Andhra Pradesh In registration of deeds as manual systems are involved problems like valuation of property, assessment of duty, lack of transparency in valuation of projects, deterioration of quality in storage of paper based documents. The Project CARD helped to overcome all the problems that are there in the manual system. After Implementation of the CARD project 10 million citizens benefited within 3 years. Few of the benefits like transparency in valuation of properties, speed, reliability, consistency and efficient document management system.

E-SEVA Project in Andhra Pradesh: E-Seva is the project launched by the AP Government to provide one stop shop solutions and services to citizens. This is the best model for G2C. The project is implemented with the help of Public Private Partnership (PPP). The services like payment of electricity, telephone bills, water bills, payment of taxes, ticket reservations, passport applications, registration of birth and death, payments by cash/card/cheque are some of the services provided to citizens.

BHOOMI Project in Karnataka: Karnataka being an agriculture oriented state faced with the problem of maintaining immense land records and entire process is done by manually. This project facilitated to computerize entire 20 million records of land ownership of 6.7 million farmers in the state of Karnataka. At present land record kiosks called Bhoomi center is functional in all the 177 talukas in the state.

AKSHAYA Project in Kerala: Kerala is renowned as one of the most literate states in the south India. But failed in catching up with the IT literacy owing government inability to promote and create an interest in the public. In 2002 Kerala government launched Paramashivaiah and Suresh / OIDA International Journal of Sustainable Development 09:08 (2016) 15 Akshaya Project to promote IT

literacy. With in no time attracted public became very successful. One of its most recent achievements was to become one of the finalists in the prestigious Stockholm Challenge award for 2004.

The National E-Governance Plan

The National E-Governance Plan (NeGP) is an initiative of the Government of India to make all government services available to the citizens of India via electronic media. NeGP was formulated by the Department of Electronics and Information Technology (DeitY) and Department of Administrative Reforms and Public Grievances (DARPG). The Government approved the National e-Governance Plan, consisting of 27 "Mission Mode Projects" (MMPs) and Ten components, on 18 May 2006. This is an enabler of Digital India initiative, and UMANG (Unified Mobile Application for New-age Governance) in turn is an enabler of NeGP. Table 1.1 depicts the online services provided under the (NeGP).

Analysis of Impact on Indian Economy

a) Reduction of Cost in Service Delivery

Although many applications in developing countries have shown significant benefits, in general, cost reduction has not taken place. In most cases E-Government becomes an additional channel to offer services. Even in developed countries where internet penetration is high, the proportion of citizens using portal for services is low. Until this proportion reaches a level that there can be some cut back in the number of personnel employed in delivering services through the traditional departmental channel or telephone, there will be little reduction in costs. In fact initially the costs will rise on account of investments in organizing electronic delivery. In the developed countries, privacy and security issues seem to be holding the citizens back. In the developing countries the Internet penetrations are very low.

b) Control of Government Expenditure

Many countries have implemented integrate financial management systems to track and control payments made out of Government treasuries. For example the state of Karnataka has connected all its 215 treasuries through a satellite based net. Every payment is now centrally authenticated to ensure that a budget provision exists for the payment and that it is not exceeded. Such systems focus on expenditure control, not exploiting the full potential of the system to combat corruption and improve service delivery. Experience suggests that it is difficult to implement IFIMIS as they are complex and need to be comprehensive in their scope to deliver concrete benefits. Another strategy to control expenditure is to introduce paper less offices in large Government departments (see eSAT in Mexico, Smartgov in Andhra Pradesh). A few of such applications have been implemented.

c) Growth of tax Revenue

The inefficient collection of taxes in many developing countries has led to cash-strapped governments that are incapable of enforcing tax payments. Moreover, corruption in the collection process leads to less money going to the government and lack of public confidence in the system. Modernizing Tax Systems through E-Government applications has been a priority for many countries. Through online tax filing and processing system, governments aim to reduce the corruption and enhance transparency to create more public trust. Computerized interstate check posts in Gujarat, India, have resulted in three-fold increase in tax collection over 2 years. Revenue increased from \$12 million to \$50 million, paying back the total project costs of \$34 million in just 6 months (Vijayalaxmi & Padma, 2003).

CONCLUSION

As the usage of Information Technology is growing very fast, Indian government is making many efforts to provide services to its citizens through e-Governance. Although Indian government is spending a lot of money on e-Governance projects but still these projects are not successful in all parts of India. Unawareness in people, local language of the people of a particular area, privacy for the personal data of the people etc. are main challenges which are responsible for the unsuccessful implementation of e-Governance in India. Government must take some actions to make the people aware about the e-Governance activities so that people may take full advantage of these activities and e-Governance projects can be implemented successfully. The participation of people can play a vital role in implementation of e-Governance in India.

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